

Reading culture

Termiz State University

Faculty of national dress and art

Organization and management of cultural and art institutions

3rd year student

Ikromov Azizbek Akmal o'g'li

Key words: creativity, educational value of books, book reading, publishing activities, library services.

ABSTRACT: in the article, it is mentioned about raising reading culture in the education of the young generation. In addition, it is mentioned that the book is the main source for spiritual and moral nourishment, culture and language development in the society today.

The educational importance of the book in raising a perfect generation is incomparable. Therefore, it is precisely reading that gives knowledge and information to a person, and enriches his spiritual world. A good book is a happy tool for finding answers to the most difficult questions.

According to "NOP World" international rating agency, people in the world spend 16.6 hours a week watching TV, 8.9 hours in front of the computer, and 6.5 hours for reading. In 2016, in the list of countries with the most books per week, India — 10.7, Thailand — 9.4, China — 8, Philippines — 7.6, Czech Republic — 7.4, Russia — 7.1, Sweden - 6.9, France - 6.9 and Hungary - 6.8 hours took the top places.

The fact that publishing activities are developing and book reading is becoming more popular shows that the idea that people will lose interest in reading books as audio, video means of communication, radio, television, and information communication networks occupy a deep place in our lives is a mistake. Undoubtedly, as a result of the emergence of new types of mass media, reading has somewhat decreased, but the press serves to increase people's interest in reading books.

The study of the demand for books in the world by a number of agencies showed that in the last 30 years, the release of book products of the same name has increased three times, and the number has increased four times. Today, about one million books are published in the world every year. For example, 10 books are printed per person in the USA, 9.5 in Russia, 5 in France, and 3.5 in China.

Modern legal foundations of publishing have been created in our country. During the past period, more than 10 laws and more than 30 legal documents were adopted. 1,677 printing enterprises, 118 publishing houses were registered with the state. The National Library of Uzbekistan named after Alisher Navoi, equipped with advanced technologies, 14 regional information-library centers, about 200 information-resource centers in educational institutions in cities, and "World of Books", "Sharq zyokori" and "Ozdavkitobsavtotaminoti" complexes have established a book sales service. The "Ijod" public fund, established under the Writers' Union of Uzbekistan, publishes many thousands of copies of the first books of writers and poets, especially young artists.

Today, in society, there is a need to preserve and even restore the position and importance of the book as the main resource for spiritual and moral nourishment, culture and language development, as an intellectual heritage passed down from generation to generation. First of all, a well-thought-out system for publishing artistic, educational, scientific-popular, educational, literature aimed at increasing the intellectual potential of young people, providing educational

institutions with them, sorting and translating the works of national and world literary figures. should be organized on the basis of In addition, it is necessary to stimulate the interest of the young generation in books.

The decrease in interest in reading, in turn, the decrease in the level of literacy of the population is one of the biggest threats to the sustainable development of society and the state. That is why many developed countries are taking strict measures to prevent this negative situation. Develops nationwide complex programs. They include systematic measures to unify the efforts of state authorities and administrative bodies, libraries, educational institutions, educational, scientific and business entities, civil society institutions in the field, and mass media. events will be viewed. In this regard, special attention is paid to the formation of social consciousness about the value and importance of reading, targeted support and development of reading culture among different strata of the population, improvement of publishing activities, formation of a book market that fully meets the intellectual, spiritual and cultural needs of society. 'attention is being paid. According to world experience, the adoption of such targeted programs and concepts gives positive results.

In this sense, the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 12, 2017 "On the establishment of a commission on the development of the system of printing and distribution of book products, on the promotion and promotion of book reading and reading culture" it is important in that it is aimed at the comprehensive solution of the problems that have arisen in this regard. Currently, a special working group is developing a project of a complex program of measures to develop the system of printing and distribution of book products, to increase the culture of book reading and reading, and to promote it. In this process, special emphasis is placed on the measures to popularize reading, improve the system of improving the skills of children and young people, and monitor the state of reading.

In order to popularize book reading, public events to attract a wide population to book reading and provide them with books, organization of charity campaigns, effective use of social advertising, promotion of classic and modern works of Uzbek and world literature, well-known authors It is planned to carry out specific work on supporting public initiatives in this field, developing the movement of volunteers, and organizing a broad public discussion of the problem of reading, including using social networks and the internet. is being held.

It should be noted that acquainting children with books, educating them in the spirit of love for reading, instilling in the minds of teenagers and young adults that reading books is an effective and influential tool for achieving their goals and social adaptation to society is one of the most urgent tasks today. With this in mind, the program includes the publication of books for children and adolescents, including support for the production of special e-books, the modernization and further improvement of the collections of children's and school libraries, the use of children's and adolescents in libraries, out-of-school and measures to encourage summer reading, restore and popularize family reading traditions, promote the best examples of children's and youth literature, encourage reading in one's mother tongue is being entered.

Libraries will be modernized due to the introduction of new information and communication technologies, strengthening of their material and technical base, further improvement of the book fund. In order to facilitate the citizens who live in remote settlements and have limited access to libraries, to develop mobile library services, establish inter-library subscriptions and electronic delivery of documents, remote access to library resources,

systematically organize individual, group and public reading in these places of interest. specific mechanisms for developing the organization, educating the culture of reading, making people familiar with high artistic works, and improving the image of libraries in our country are proposed.

To develop the system of personnel training and their professional development as well as the reading infrastructure, to conduct fundamental and practical research on the history and modern trends of book culture, to promote reading among different strata of the population, especially among those who are somewhat distant from reading books. Development of strategy and tactics is one of the urgent tasks.

These measures, first of all, are aimed at increasing the reading culture of the population, further updating libraries, increasing the number and quality of literary works of social importance, developing the system of distribution and delivery of book products.

In conclusion, the growth of reading in society is primarily a factor of spiritual and moral growth of the individual. This serves the growth of the intellectual potential of our people, the improvement of the quality of human resources, and the socio-economic and innovative development of our republic.

Recommended literature

1. Islam KARIMOV "High spirituality is an invincible power"
2. Lex.uz

